

A faunistic study on Tenebrionidae (Coleoptera: Tenebrionoidea) of Iran

Studium faunistyczne czarnuchowatych (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) Iranu

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ABSTRACT: This paper deals with the fauna of Tenebrionidae (Coleoptera) from some regions of Iran. In total, 15 species within four subfamilies, Diaperinae (one species), Lagriinae (one species), Pimeliinae (five species, five genera) and Tenebrioninae (eight species, eight genera) were collected and identified. Ten species are new records for the fauna of Iran.

KEY WORDS: darkling beetles, fauna, distribution, new records.

Introduction

The family Tenebrionidae LATREILLE, 1802 is the fifth largest family of beetles, with approximately 20,000 described species worldwide, and around 8,000 species in the Palaearctic Region. Tenebrionidae are a dominant part of many insect faunas, from deserts to rainforests (STEINER 2008; IWAN & al. 2020). The Tenebrionidae, often commonly referred to as darkling beetles, generally feed on material of plant origin including decaying matter, wood, leaf litter, pollen, as well as fungal and algal matter. Some are also scavengers while very few species are predatory especially of wood boring beetles. A small number of species are myrmecophilous. Some species as cosmopolitan pests and have become associated with stored grain products (MIFSUD & SCUPOLA 1998; LILLIG & al. 2012).

The fauna of Iranian Tenebrionidae has poorly been studied so far (MEDVDEV & MERKL 2005; TARAVATI & FERRER 2007, SAKENIN & al. 2009; GHAHARI & al. 2010a, 2010b, 2012; GHAHARI & BUNALSKI 2011; BUNALSKI & al. 2014a, 2014b; NABOTHIAN 2015a, 2015b; BUNALSKI & GHAHARI 2017). Additionally, about the checklist of Iranian

Tenebrionidae (MODARRES AWAL 1997, 2012) both listed 31 species for the fauna of Iran.

The purpose of this paper is to record the species of Tenebrionidae from some regions of Iran as part of ongoing faunistic studies of Tenebrionidae in Iran.

Material and methods

The specimens were collected under stones and on the ground by hand and knock down, sweeping of vegetation and pitfall trap methods during occasional field surveys from the different regions of Iran. The collected specimens were killed by ethyl acetate within killing bottle and then pinned, or were put in alcohol (ethanol 75%) and determined by J. FERRER (Sweden). Information concerning date of collection, locality, and number of specimens are given. Some of the specimens are preserved in Bugsland of Jurassic Park (Tehran, Iran) and some others in the private collection of J. FERRER. The classification, nomenclature and distribution suggested by IWAN & al. (2020) have been followed.

Results

In this faunistic paper, totally 20 species of Tenebrionidae within 18 genera were identified as the fauna of Iran. Ten species are represented as new

country records. The list of species is given below alphabetically with distributional data.

Fig. Map of Iran with provincial boundaries, and distribution of Tenebrionidae of this research (the numerals refer to species number in the paper).

Ryc. Mapa Iranu z podziałem na prowincje i lokalizacją stanowisk badawczych (numeracja odpowiada numerom gatunków w tekście).

Subfamily Diaperinae LATREILLE, 1802

Tribe Crypticini BRULLÉ, 1832

Genus *Alphitophagus* STEPHENS, 1832

1. *Alphitophagus bifasciatus* SAY, 1824

Distribution. AFRICA: Egypt, Tunisia; ASIA: Afghanistan, China, Cyprus, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Syria, Taiwan, Turkey, Turkmenistan; EUROPE: Albania, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Rep., Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania,

Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine.

Material examined: Golestan prov., Golestan National Park, IV 2013, 3 exx.

New record for Iran.

Subfamily Lagriinae LATREILLE, 1825

Tribe Laenini SEIDLITZ, 1896

Genus *Laena* DEJEAN, 1821

2. *Laena hirtipes* REITTER, 1881

Distribution. ASIA: Iran; EUROPE: Azerbaijan.

Material examined: East Azarbayjan prov., Arasbaran forest, IX 2012, 2 exx.

Subfamily Pimeliinae LATREILLE, 1802

Tribe Adelostomini SOLIER, 1834

Genus *Adelostoma* DUPONCHEL, 1827

3. *Adelostoma (Adelostoma) sulcata sulcata* DUPONCHEL, 1827

Distribution. AFRICA: Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco; ASIA: Cyprus, Iraq, Israel, Syria, Turkey; EUROPE: Croatia, Spain.

Material examined: Ilam prov., Abdanan, IV 2012, 2 exx.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Pimeliini LATREILLE, 1802

Genus *Pachyscelis* SOLIER, 1836

4. *Pachyscelis (Parapachyscelis) villosa* DRAPIEZ, 1820
Distribution. AFRICA: Egypt; ASIA: Iran, Iraq, Israel, Syria, Turkey; EUROPE: Greece.

Material examined: Kermanshah prov., Gilan-gharb, IV 2011, 1 ex.

Genus *Pimelia* FABRICIUS, 1775

5. *Pimelia (Camphonota) akbesiana akbesiana* FAIRMAIRE, 1884

Distribution. ASIA: Iran, Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: Kurdistan prov., Baneh, IV 2013, 2 exx.

Tribe Stenosini LACORDAIRE, 1859

Genus *Aspidocephalus* MOTSCHULSKY, 1839

6. *Aspidocephalus desertus* MOTSCHULSKY, 1839

Distribution. ASIA: Kazakhstan; EUROPE: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia.

Material examined: Gilan prov., Talesh, V 2011, 3 exx.

New record for Iran.

Genus *Eutagenia* REITTER, 1886

7. *Eutagenia smyrnensis* (SOLIER, 1838)

Distribution. ASIA: Iran, Jordan, Syria, Turkey; EUROPE: Bulgaria, Greece.

Material examined: East Azarbayjan prov., Maragheh, VII 2013, 3 exx.

Subfamily Tenebrioninae LATREILLE, 1802

Tribe Alphitobiini REITTER, 1917

Genus *Alphitobius* STEPHENS, 1829

8. *Alphitobius laevigatus* (FABRICIUS, 1781)

Distribution. AFRICA: Canary Isl., Egypt, Libya, Madeira, Tunisia; ASIA: Afghanistan, Bahrain, Bhutan, China, Cyprus, Iraq, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Russia, Taiwan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen; EUROPE: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Azores, Belgium, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Khorasan Shomali prov., 6 km Lujely-Shirvan, V 2011, 4 exx.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Blaptini LEACH, 1815

Subtribe Blaptina LEACH, 1815

Genus *Blaps* FABRICIUS, 1775

9. *Blaps (Blaps) gigas* LINNAEUS, 1767

Distribution. AFRICA: Algeria, Canary Isl., Libya, Madeira, Tunisia; ASIA: Iraq, Kazakhstan, Turkey; EUROPE: Albania, Austria, Azores, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Rep., France, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Material examined: Kurdistan prov., Bijar, VIII 2015, 2 exx.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Opatrini BRULLÉ, 1832

Subtribe Opatrina BRULLÉ, 1832

Genus *Opatrum* FABRICIUS, 1775

10. *Opatrum (Opatrum) verrucosum* GERMAR, 1817

Distribution. ASIA: Turkey; EUROPE: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Serbia and Montenegro, Turkey.

Material examined: Ardabil prov., Aslandooz, VI 2012, 1 ex.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Palorini MATTHEWS, 2003

Genus *Palorus* MULSANT, 1854

11. *Palorus depressus* FABRICIUS, 1790

Distribution. AFRICA: Egypt; ASIA: Japan, Kazakhstan, Taiwan, Tajikistan, Turkey; EUROPE: Albania, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Material examined: Southern Khorasan prov., Ferdows, IV 2013, 2 exx.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Pedinini ESCHSCHOLTZ, 1829

Subtribe Pedinina ESCHSCHOLTZ, 1829

Genus *Cabirutus* STRAND, 1929

12. *Cabirutus (Cabirutus) gracilis* (REITTER, 1904)

Distribution. ASIA: Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: Kurdistan prov., Bijar, VIII 2015, 1 ex.

New record for Iran.

Genus *Colpotus* MULSANT et REY, 1853

13. *Colpotus vogti* KOCH, 1948

Distribution. ASIA: Turkey; EUROPE: Greece.

Material examined: West Azarbayjan prov., Mahabad, VIII 2014, 1 ex.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Scaurini BILLBERG, 1820

Genus *Cephalostenus* SOLIER, 1836

14. *Cephalostenus elegans* (BRULLÉ, 1832)

Distribution. ASIA: Turkey; EUROPE: Greece.

Material examined: West Azarbayjan prov., Oshnavieh, VIII 2014, 2 exx.

New record for Iran.

Tribe Triboliini GISTEL, 1848

Genus *Latheticus* WATERHOUSE, 1880

15. *Latheticus oryzae* WATERHOUSE, 1880

Distribution. AFRICA: Canary Isl., Libya, Morocco, Tunisia; ASIA: China, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Taiwan, Turkmenistan, Yemen; EUROPE: Austria, Belgium, Czech Rep., Denmark, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Material examined: Lorestan prov., Noor-Abad, VI 2013, 3 exx.

Discussion

In this research, totally 32 specimens were collected from 11 provinces of north and north-western parts of Iran (Fig.). The fauna of Iranian Tenebrionidae has poorly been studied while Iran with 1,623,779 km² is the 18th largest country in the world and is characterized by various geographical regions and high climatic heterogeneity (ZEHZAD & al. 2002; HAKIMZADEH KHOEI & al. 2011). Among the different subfamilies of Iranian Tenebrionidae, only Alleculinae was studied well by NOVÁK &

GHAHARI (2015) and other subfamilies have not been studied perfectly so far. However, the zoo-geographical picture of tenebrionid fauna is far from complete because the fauna of most regions of Iran is inadequately known. Faunistic surveys on these insects must be continued in different regions of Iran especially in east and southern areas which will result to new findings (new country records, new distributional data, and probably new species). The faunistic works are necessary in order to completing the fauna of Iranian Tenebrionidae step by step.

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STRESZCZENIE

W trakcie badań entomologicznych prowadzonych w latach 2011-2015 w 11 północnych prowincjach Iranu (ryc.) zebrano bogaty materiał faunistyczny. Powyższe opracowanie obejmuje 15 gatunków Tenebrionidae należących do 4 podrodzajów: Diaperinae, Lagriinae, Pimeliinae i Tenebrioninae. Dla każdego z gatunków podano ogólne rozmieszczenie, dane faunistyczne oraz okalzację na mapie Iranu. Dziesięć z omawianych gatunków nie były do tej pory podawanych z Iranu (IWAN i in. 2020).

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